

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MODERN DIAGNOSTIC METHODS USED IN DETECTION OF CYTOMEGALOVIRUS

Mammadov P.

Institution: V. Akhundov National Scientific Research Medical Prophylactic Institute Azerbaijan

Profession: Chief laborant

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7788709>

Abstract

Human cytomegalovirus (HCMV), a betaherpes virus, is a major cause of birth defects and an important pathogen in immunocompromised individuals. Clinical symptoms may appear after initial infection, reinfection, or reactivation. Human cytomegalovirus (HCMV) usually does not cause obvious symptoms. Modern diagnostic methods indicate that HCMV is a widespread opportunistic infection in fetuses, bone marrow transplant patients, and AIDS patients. In this article, we will review the diagnostic methods used for cytomegalovirus.

Keywords: cytomegalovirus, diagnosis, virus, methods, herpes

Human cytomegalovirus (HCMV), a betaherpes virus, is a major cause of birth defects and an important pathogen in immunocompromised individuals. A virus with a linear double-stranded DNA genome of 230 kb is surrounded by a viral nucleocapsid and a bilayered lipid supercapsid. Clinical symptoms may appear after initial infection, reinfection, or reactivation (1). Human cytomegalovirus (HCMV) usually does not cause obvious symptoms. Modern diagnostic methods indicate that HCMV is a widespread opportunistic infection in fetuses, bone marrow transplant patients, and AIDS patients. The virus is not as harmless as it seems, as it sometimes results in death (2). Human cytomegalovirus (HCMV) causes serious disease primarily in immunocompromised individuals, particularly allograft recipients and premature infants, as well as in patients infected during pregnancy (congenital HCMV [cCMV]). These include pneumonitis, retinitis, hepatitis, sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) in infants, and mental retardation (3). In healthy children and adults, HCMV infection is often mild, but the virus causes about 10% of cases of infectious mononucleosis (Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) infection). Diagnostic tests are critical to confirm cCMV, monitor viral infections and immune responses among organ transplant (SOT) and hematopoietic stem cell transplant (HSCT) recipients.

The basic principle of laboratory tests for the diagnosis of HCMV infections in the context of organ or hematopoietic stem cell transplantation is based on the direct detection of the virus and the measurement of the body's immune responses. Laboratory tests that directly detect HCMV are recommended for surveillance, diagnosis, and monitoring. For HCMV risk assessment and risk factor stratification, analysis of immune status is based.

Analyzes for virus detection.

Direct detection of HCMV in clinical specimens is the standard method for diagnosing HCMV infection in transplant patients (4). The most widespread method for direct detection of the virus is quantitative nucleic acid amplification tests (QNAT) with high sensitivity and quick results. Detection and quantification of the HCMV genome is possible using this test (5). Blood and plasma samples are mainly used for HCMV-QNAT

analysis. Sometimes cerebrospinal fluid and bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) are used. HCMV QNAT testing of blood or plasma is more appropriate for use in diagnosing diseases such as pneumonia or gastrointestinal disease, and when obtaining biopsy specimens for histopathology is risky (5).

Diagnosis of Maternal and Congenital CMV Infections.

cCMV infections are a major cause of SNHL and neurological disability in children. cCMV infection can follow primary and non-primary infection of the mother during pregnancy. Infected seronegative mothers are the greatest risk factor during pregnancy. Transmission to the fetus occurs in about 32% of these cases and causes disease in about 13% of congenitally infected newborns (6). Among HCMV seropositive women, reactivation of an endogenous HCMV strain or reinfection with another strain of the virus causes fetal infection in approximately 1% of pregnancies. This rate is much lower than for primary infections, but reactivation and reinfections are more common. As a result, HCMV-seropositive women are the main source of congenital infections worldwide (7). Primary and non-primary maternal infections can cause serious consequences (6). If there is no effective vaccine against the disease, then other forms of prevention are needed. Several studies suggest that avoiding contact with bodily fluids of children can reduce HCMV seroconversion in pregnant women (8). Based on data from such cohort or case-control analytical studies, The International Congenital Cytomegalovirus Recommendation Group has recommended that, "all pregnant women should be educated about congenital cytomegalovirus infections and preventive measures" (9). Related to this, the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention's guidance to health care providers states that "Avoiding contact with saliva and urine from young children might reduce the risk of CMV infection, although research studies don't provide a clear answer. Some examples of how to avoid contact include kissing children on the cheek or head rather than the lips and washing hands after changing diapers." (10). Clinical diagnosis of maternal HCMV infection is unreliable because most pregnant

women with active infection are asymptomatic; therefore, laboratory diagnosis is the primary approach to identify women with primary HCMV infection (11).

Serology.

Although various HCMV serological methods are indicated as basic research methods, their inclusion in clinical diagnostic algorithms requires careful evaluation and interpretation. As a result of prenatal immunological diagnostic analyses, HCMV immunological parameters among pregnant women show individual variability. Therefore, immunological data are not reliable for determining the risk of fetal HCMV transmission. However, since the majority of maternal HCMV infections are asymptomatic, detection of women at risk of transmission of the virus to the fetus depends on the implementation of serological and virological tests early in pregnancy (before 12-14 weeks of pregnancy) (12).

Nucleic acid test.

Detection of primary HCMV in body fluids in immunocompromised individuals is primary in pregnant women but secondary in the diagnosis of HCMV infection. It can often be used to confirm a serological diagnosis. Data suggest that detection and quantification of HCMV-DNA in maternal body fluids may be useful for predicting intrauterine transmission in women with primary infection. Women who transmit the virus to their fetuses are about 2 times more likely to shed CMV-DNA in their blood, cervical secretions, and urine (13, 14).

Non-primary HCMV infection is difficult to diagnose. Serological testing is not the basis for identifying non-primary infections. Laboratory tests play a role in the diagnosis of non-primary HCMV infection in women with known serological status prior to pregnancy. However, extensive prospective studies are needed to determine the optimal time of sample collection, evaluation of serological tests, detection of viral DNA in various body fluids, development and validation of algorithms.

Prenatal Diagnosis of HCMV Infection.

Both invasive and non-invasive prenatal diagnosis are offered to pregnant women at high risk of HCMV transmission to the fetus, especially pregnant women with confirmed primary infection during pregnancy and abnormal ultrasound findings suggestive of cCMV infection. (15).

Invasive prenatal testing is performed for a variety of reasons, but the most common indication is fetal genetic testing (17). Quantification of viral DNA in amniotic fluid (AF) is the most appropriate method for diagnosing fetal HCMV infection (15). AF qPCR sensitivity decreases from 100% specificity to 80–90% when amniosynthesis is performed at least 8 weeks after the onset of maternal infection and after at least 20–21 weeks of gestation (16). Although high viral loads in AFs are associated with symptomatic or asymptomatic cCMV, high viral loads suggest the possibility of more severe disease (18).

Non-invasive prenatal diagnosis (NIPD) aims to detect fetal genetic disorders before birth by detecting markers in the peripheral blood of pregnant women, with the potential to reduce the risk of fetal birth defects (19). When fetal HCMV status is known, ultrasound is

useful for detecting and monitoring fetal abnormalities, such as brain abnormalities that are indicative of severe disease. (20).

It is difficult to determine the exact result for an infected fetus with no or mild abnormalities on ultrasound examination until about 30 weeks' gestation. (21).

Cell culture.

This method was used to detect CMV by immunofluorescence (IF) method in cell culture with monoclonal antibody against CMV antigen. Detection of early CMV antigen in cell culture is considered the fastest method (22).

Testing of saliva samples.

Oral saliva real-time polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) has been shown to be sensitive and specific for the detection of congenital cytomegalovirus (cCMV). Targeted screening RT-PCR testing for cCMV has high sensitivity but low positive predictive value and therefore requires additional confirmatory testing (23).

References:

1. Landolfo, S., Gariglio, M., Gribaudo, G., & Lembo, D. (2003). The human cytomegalovirus. *Pharmacology & therapeutics*, 98(3), 269-297.
2. Rubin, R. H. (1989). The indirect effects of cytomegalovirus infection on the outcome of organ transplantation. *Jama*, 261(24), 3607-3609.
3. R Schleiss, M. (2011). Congenital cytomegalovirus infection: molecular mechanisms mediating viral pathogenesis. *Infectious Disorders-Drug Targets (Formerly Current Drug Targets-Infectious Disorders)*, 11(5), 449-465.
4. Razonable, R. R., & Humar, A. (2019). Cytomegalovirus in solid organ transplant recipients—Guidelines of the American Society of Transplantation Infectious Diseases Community of Practice. *Clinical transplantation*, 33(9), e13512.
5. Beam, E., Germer, J. J., Lahr, B., Yao, J. D., Limper, A. H., Binnicker, M. J., & Razonable, R. R. (2018). Cytomegalovirus (CMV) DNA quantification in bronchoalveolar lavage fluid of immunocompromised patients with CMV pneumonia. *Clinical Transplantation*, 32(1), e13149.
6. Emery, V. C., & Lazzarotto, T. (2017). Cytomegalovirus in pregnancy and the neonate. *F1000Research*, 6.
7. de Vries, J. J., van Zwet, E. W., Dekker, F. W., Kroes, A. C., Verkerk, P. H., & Vossen, A. C. (2013). The apparent paradox of maternal seropositivity as a risk factor for congenital cytomegalovirus infection: a population-based prediction model. *Reviews in medical virology*, 23(4), 241-249.
8. Revello, M. G., Tibaldi, C., Masuelli, G., Frisina, V., Sacchi, A., Furione, M., ... & Todros, T. (2015). Prevention of primary cytomegalovirus infection in pregnancy. *EBioMedicine*, 2(9), 1205-1210.
9. Rawlinson, W. D., Boppana, S. B., Fowler, K. B., Kimberlin, D. W., Lazzarotto, T., Alain, S., ... & van Zuylen, W. J. (2017). Congenital cytomegalovirus

infection in pregnancy and the neonate: consensus recommendations for prevention, diagnosis, and therapy. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*, 17(6), e177-e188.

10. Talking with pregnant patients about CMV: Resource for healthcare providers. (n.d.). March 13, 2023.

11. Razonable, R. R., Inoue, N., Pinninti, S. G., Boppana, S. B., Lazzarotto, T., Gabrielli, L., ... & Schmid, D. S. (2020). Clinical diagnostic testing for human cytomegalovirus infections. *The Journal of infectious diseases*, 221(Supplement_1), S74-S85.

12. Leruez-Ville, M., & Ville, Y. (2017). Fetal cytomegalovirus infection. *Best practice & research Clinical obstetrics & gynaecology*, 38, 97-107.

13. Delforge, M. L., Costa, E., Brancart, F., Goldman, D., Montesinos, I., Zaytouni, S., ... & Donner, C. (2017). Presence of cytomegalovirus in urine and blood of pregnant women with primary infection might be associated with fetal infection. *Journal of Clinical Virology*, 90, 14-17.

14. Tanimura, K., Tairaku, S., Ebina, Y., Morioka, I., Nagamata, S., Deguchi, K., ... & Yamada, H. (2017). Prediction of congenital cytomegalovirus infection in high-risk pregnant women. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 64(2), 159-165.

15. Lazzarotto, T., Guerra, B., Gabrielli, L., Lanari, M., & Landini, M. P. (2011). Update on the prevention, diagnosis and management of cytomegalovirus infection during pregnancy. *Clinical Microbiology and Infection*, 17(9), 1285-1293.

16. Enders, M., Daiminger, A., Exler, S., & Enders, G. (2017). Amniocentesis for prenatal diagnosis of cytomegalovirus infection: challenging the 21 weeks' threshold. *Prenatal diagnosis*, 37(9), 940-942.

17. Bringman, J. J. (2014). Invasive prenatal genetic testing: A Catholic healthcare provider's perspective. *The Linacre Quarterly*, 81(4), 302-313.

18. Leruez-Ville, M., Stirnemann, J., Sellier, Y., Guilleminot, T., Dejean, A., Magny, J. F., ... & Ville, Y. (2016). Feasibility of predicting the outcome of fetal infection with cytomegalovirus at the time of prenatal diagnosis. *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology*, 215(3), 342-e1.

19. Chen, Y., Wu, Z., Sutlive, J., Wu, K., Mao, L., Nie, J., ... & Huang, Q. (2022). Noninvasive prenatal diagnosis targeting fetal nucleated red blood cells. *Journal of Nanobiotechnology*, 20(1), 546.

20. Picone O, Vauloup-Fellous C, Cordier AG, Guitton S, Senat MV, Fuchs F, Ayoubi JM, Grangeot Keros L, Benachi A. A series of 238 cytomegalovirus primary infections during pregnancy: description and outcome. *Prenat Diagn*. 2013 Aug;33(8):751-8.

21. Capretti, M. G., Lanari, M., Tani, G., Ancora, G., Sciutti, R., Marsico, C., ... & Faldella, G. (2014). Role of cerebral ultrasound and magnetic resonance imaging in newborns with congenital cytomegalovirus infection. *Brain and Development*, 36(3), 203-211.

22. Wirgart, B. Z., & Grillner, L. (1986). Early detection of cytomegalovirus in cell culture by a monoclonal antibody. *Journal of virological methods*, 14(1), 65-69.

23. Eventov-Friedman, S., Manor, H., Bar-Oz, B., Averbuch, D., Caplan, O., Lifshitz, A., ... & Wolf, D. G. (2019). Saliva real-time polymerase chain reaction for targeted screening of congenital cytomegalovirus infection. *The Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 220(11), 1790-1796.